

ISic0714

I.Sicily inscription 0714

Language

Latin and Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331951

1. de p [osita in pace (?)]

2. Const a [ntia (?) — — —]

3. fecit η [erenti — con]-

4. sorti Mani [lius (?) — —]

5. λ

6. ἐν[θάδ]ε κίτε ἐν ἰ [ρήνη (nomen)]

7. ἡ [ἀξιολο]γωτάτη, ἥτις [ἔζησε]

8. [ἔτη τριά]κοντα· τελευτ [ᾶ τῆ]

9. [πρ(ὸ) εἰδῶ]ν Ὀκτωβρίων ὑπ (ατία) Β[αλεν]-

10. [τιαν]οῦ Ἀγούστου ²⁶Αύγούστου²⁶ τὸ η ἔζ [ησε]

11. [(nomen)]ῆ μετ' ἔμοῦ Ἄξ (ίου) Προ σ [ή]-

12. [νους ἐ]ν ὀμοζυγία ἔτη θ. □

13.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644829

PHI 331951

Bibliography

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